

**THE PLACE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF PHYSICAL
EDUCATION IN OUR LIFE**
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Annotation: In today's article, we will focus on strengthening the health of employees and increase their labor productivity, physical production is the goal of education. It is mainly an enterprise, organization, association during working hours and during non-working hours. Form it organized and independent, grouped and mixed can be carried out, physical education in production and general conditions for the development of health training to be created by the management of the enterprise and public organizations a must.

Key word: Production physical education from general health in addition to special issues: preparing a person for work, during work and after that, recovery of working capacity, active work and is aimed at solving other issues.

Аннотация: В сегодняшней статье речь пойдет об укреплении здоровья сотрудников и повышении производительности их труда, физическое производство является целью воспитания. В основном это предприятия, организации, объединения в рабочее и нерабочее время. Форма его может быть организованной и самостоятельной, групповой и смешанной, физическое воспитание на производстве и общие условия для развития санитарной подготовки должны быть созданы руководством предприятия и общественными организациями.

Ключевые слова: Производственная физическая культура направлена не только на общие оздоровительные вопросы, но и на специальные вопросы: подготовка человека к труду, во время работы и после нее, восстановление трудоспособности, активная работа и направлена на решение других вопросов.

Introduction. It is known that training the young generation and raising them to be physically healthy attention is drawn from school age. Of course, it is taught in schools the role and importance of the science of physical education is extremely great. After all, the body is healthy only then the mind will be healthy.[1,10,8,9,13,6]Physical education is national of the peoples of the Republic of Uzbekistan an integral part of culture, physical and spiritual maturity is an important means of friendship between the peoples of the republic serves the work of strengthening, social and economic development. This manual is about physical education and sports for higher education institutions that do not train specialists Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan the decision of the meeting of the coordinated council on March 29, 2003 Based on DTS and model program approved by Physical education of undergraduate students of the higher educational institution in the guide theoretical knowledge that is necessary for mastering in the science of education, as well as independent in the free time of students during class and after class practical tips for their engagement have been reflected.[11,17,18] Also, Olympic games, movement and Olympic philosophy, History of physical education in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan and development, World and Asian championships of Uzbekistan athletes details about his participation in international competitions information is provided.^[1] The social essence of physical education means increasing the ability to work. This includes industrial gymnastics, various exercises and games during breaks, sports training on the day off, trips and other direct services. The role of physical education in the implementation of aesthetic education has its own characteristics. This is expressed in dances, ballet, circus, and games such as prancing. In the art of singing, physical exercises are widely used in order to deepen breathing and train the throat with fresh air. Artistic, rhythmic (aerobic) gymnastics, jumping on a trampoline, swimming, underwater gymnastics (synchronized swimming), ice skating and other fields of art, aesthetic aspects are related to physical education and sports. [9,7,4,5]When using physical education and sports for health purposes, the healing forces of nature (water, air,

sun) and hygienic requirements are fully observed. For this reason, natural and special processes related to human activity are embodied in the socio-educational features of physical education and sports.

Discussion and results: In the socio-educational features of physical education and sports, health measures are a social-pedagogical process of great importance. On this basis, the training of specialized personnel in the field of physical education and sports is considered an important process of state importance. This, in turn, is related to meeting the needs of physical education and sports activities, further improving the socio-cultural conditions of the population. In this way, the activities carried out by the President and the Government of the Republic are bearing their high-level results. For this reason, the number of people engaged in one or another type of physical education and sports in all strata of the population is increasing.

Research results and discussion. This is an indication of the essence of the socio-educational features of physical education and sports. [2] The social importance of physical education and sports in society It began to take a stronger place in the world community My republic is devoted to physical education and sports as well as other fields special attention is being paid. From time immemorial, our country has been to the world famous wrestlers, riders who surprised everyone, sheryurak He came with his boys and girls. (About Jlar our great grandfather Starting from Alisher Navoi, all our writers and poets, scientists my laysufs created wonderful and immortal works, poems and epics those who finished, sang songs. - World literature of Alisher Navoi of the image of Farhad, who has incomparable power, which took place from his treasure it is enough to remember oneself. And masterpieces of folk art Remember the heroes G oro Gli, Alpomish, Avazkhan, Sherali Also, Turonzamin has been a land of sherbilak and sheryuraks since ancient times b says that he has died.[2,3,5,13,12] It is historical that our republic gained the status of independence for the first time since then it has been considered one of the important factors of the development of the society Special attention was paid to

physical education and sports. My Republic was the first to establish the Order "For a Healthy Generation". of physical education and sports in our country indicates that the future is bright. Because the population is healthy The growth and development of the family will be healthy. He came from different countries united by the sports movement History is very good that people are fighters for peace knows Because sport, by its very nature, is an ambassador of peace on a global scale is doing his job. As international sports relations develop, countries and peoples mutual trust and friendly relations between them have also strengthened goes. Organization of work in one standard. Teaching in the process of physical education and sports training. The purpose of the features is to physically develop the body of students and be healthy. The way of life is to teach the requirements of forgiveness. At the same time, physical training, sports and wellness activities, specialized training helps a lot in positive learning. Physical education activities are in the morning physical education, physical education classes, club training, sports will be in the form of health competitions and celebrations. Physical education Pedagogical team of the educational institution, especially physical education teachers and sports coaches are very important. He is regularly engaged in physical education People are more resilient and disciplined than others produces many and high-quality products. Scientific organization of work and productivity improvement if the means of physical education are used correctly and regularly, quality of products produced in enterprises and institutions and the quantity increases, the work activity of workers-servants is more efficient will be. This element of the organization of work on a scientific basis is physical the influence of education brings a person to positive changes. Physical education in organizing work on a scientific basis the use of equipment has a significant positive effect on productivity shows; a short rest in increasing production efficiency periods, proper organization of work in workplaces also plays a big role. It is more related to how sports equipment is used. In production, physical culture, its aims and objectives In production, physical training tools were selected effectively and is a complex of physical exercises performed by

a person to increase the ability to work and maintain it within a certain range is directed to stay. Strengthening the health of workers and increase their labor productivity, physical production is the goal of education. It is mainly an enterprise, organization, association during working hours and during non-working hours.[1,3,18,17] Form it organized and independent, grouped and mixed can be carried out, physical education in production and general conditions for the development of health training to be created by the management of the enterprise and public organizations a must Industrial physical education from general health improvement in addition to special issues: preparing a person for work, during work and after that, recovery of working capacity, active work and It is recommended to include relaxation exercises aimed at solving other issues. ^[4]Working conditions and its organization are often exhausting determines the classification and level. Fatigue manifests itself in different ways it can. At first, lethargy, cases of drowsy pressing, continue to wor If you don't want to continue, then the person will be excited and can move freely. Therefore, recovery exercises should also be varied. First of all, dynamic exercises with a wide range of motion will help to prevent fatigue. Production in the selection of physical education exercises characteristics must be taken into account. They are of different production determines the criteria for exposure to gymnastics and special exercises. When compiling a list of physical training exercises for production enterprises, the physical condition of the employee and it is also necessary to pay attention to the development, in which physical exercises it is necessary to choose them in such a way that all those engaged in them will perform them let them get it.

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